

using the equation,

$$C = \frac{A}{\epsilon} = \frac{\text{Absorbance}}{\text{Extinction coefficient}}$$

where C = concentration in molarity, $\epsilon = 2180 \text{ l}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE 1

Migrant FeCl ₃	A	
	anionic species	cationic species
0.04 ml	0.02	0.002
	0.033	0.005
	0.021	0.002
0.08 ml	0.062	0.01
	0.064	0.01
	0.058	0.01
0.12 ml	0.210	0.017
	0.088	0.015

With these concentrations of anionic and cationic species the equilibrium constant K was calculated in each case using the equation

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HCOO}^-]^6}$$

The equilibrium constant K and its logarithm are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Migrant FeCl ₃	K	log K	Mean log K	log K from literature (e.m.f. method)
0.04 ml	640	2.81	2.83	3.1
	704	2.85		
	672	2.83		
0.08 ml	640	2.81	2.83	3.1
	661	2.82		
	619	2.79		
0.12 ml	790	2.90	2.80	
	625	2.80		

Discussion

In the presence of an excess of formate ion, the positive metal ion is complexed to form $[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}$ when the background electrolytes used are 25 ml 2M HCOONa, 1-15 ml 2M HCOOH, 50 ml 1M NaNO₃ and 24-10 ml water at the pH range 5.15 to 3.97.

But when the background electrolyte used is 25 ml 2M HCOONa, 25 ml 2M HCOOH, 50 ml 1M NaNO₃ at pH 3.75, the positive metal ion forms both the anionic and cationic species.

Electrophoretic study reports that most of the metal ion is complexed to form $[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}$ and a trace amount of metal ion moves as a simple cation. So there must exist an equilibrium

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{OOCH})_6]^{3-}}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{HCOO}^-]^6}$$

where K is the equilibrium constant.

Conclusion: Paper electrophoresis technique is limited to charged species, and the precision of the method is not as high as that of other physicochemi-

cal methods. Nevertheless, it is of interest in the metal-ligand system in solution since complex formation is widely used in effecting separations of metal ions.

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Relative Stability of Formate Complexes by Paper Electrophoresis

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STUDIES on the relative stabilities of various inorganic compounds have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. While the oxalate, citrate, tartrate and malate complexes have been investigated, none of these studies relates to the relative stability of the formate complexes. It was therefore decided to study the relative stability of formate complexes of Fe(III), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) by paper electrophoresis.

Experimental

Migrants: 2% solution of CuSO₄.5H₂O, FeCl₃.6H₂O, CoCl₂.6H₂O and NiCl₂.6H₂O were used as migrants.

Electrolytes: Stock solutions of 2M sodium formate, 2M formic acid and 1M sodium nitrate were prepared. Sodium nitrate was used to attain the desired ionic strength.

NOTES

Procedure: Whatman No. 1 (1 cm × 34 cm) paper strips were taken. The electrophoretic movement of a drop of migrant under the potential difference of 220 volts for 45 min in different carrier electrolytes are recorded in Tables 1 to 3.

It appears from Table 1 that Fe(III) and Cu(II) migrate towards the anode at high concentration (1M-0.4M) of Na-formate when pH of the carrier electrolyte is 8.9-8.7 and ionic strength is constant while Co(II) and Ni(II) ions migrate towards the cathode. It means that Fe(III) and Cu(II) ions form anionic complexes with the carrier electrolyte and Co(II) and Ni(II) do not form such complexes.

But at low concentration of sodium formate as electrolyte (0.25 M and below), Fe(III) is precipitated at the point of application, Cu(II) moves towards the cathode i.e. Cu(II) forms cationic species with the background electrolyte while Co(II) and Ni(II) behave as before.

From the resulting data, formation of M-formate and M'-formate complex, where M=Ni(II), Co(II) and M'=Fe(III), Cu(II) is inferred. The data shows that Fe(III)-formate complex is more stable than Cu(II)-formate complex. Therefore, the relative stability of Fe(III)-formate complex is higher than that of Cu(II)-formate complex.

TABLE 1

Carrier electrolyte	Distance migrated in cm ('+' anionic movement ; '-' cationic movement)			
	Fe(III)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)
(1) 50 ml 2M Na-formate + 50 ml water *(1M), pH = 8.9	+ 0.2 to + 0.9	+ 0.5 to + 2.1	- 0.7 to - 2.8	- 0.8 to - 2.4
(2) 25 ml 2M Na-formate + 25 ml water + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.5M), pH = 8.72	+ 0.2 to + 0.5	+ 0.3 to + 2	Cationic	Cationic
(3) 20 ml 2M Na-formate + 20 ml water + 60 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.4M), pH = 8.70	0 to + 0.4	+ 1.1 to - 0.5	Cationic	Cationic
(4) 12.5 ml 2M Na-formate + 12.5 ml water + 75 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.25M), pH = 8.60	ppt at the point of application	- 1.1 to - 2.7	Cationic	Cationic
(5) 5 ml 2M Na-formate + 5 ml water + 90 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.1M), pH = 8.4	ppt at the point of application	- 1.8 to - 3.2	Cationic	Cationic

pH (8.9-8.4), ionic strength constant, Na-formate variable.
*Conc. of formate in the solution and pH.

TABLE 2

Carrier electrolyte	Distance migrated in cm ('+' anionic movement ; '-' cationic movement)			
	Fe(III)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)
(1) 50 ml 2M HCOONa + 50 ml 2M HCOOH *(1M)	+ 1.9 to + 3.3	+ 2.4 to + 5.3	Cationic	Cationic
(2) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 25 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.5M)	+ 1.2 to + 2.6	+ 1.2 to - 0.5	Cationic	Cationic
(3) 20 ml 2M HCOONa + 20 ml 2M HCOOH + 60 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.4M)	+ 1.1 to + 2.3	- 0.3 to - 1.9	Cationic	Cationic
(4) 12.5 ml 2M HCOONa + 12.5 ml 2M HCOOH + 75 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.25M)	+ 0.6 to + 1.9	- 1.6 to - 2.7	Cationic	Cationic
(5) 10 ml 2M HCOONa + 10 ml 2M HCOOH + 80 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.2M)	+ 0.4 to + 2	- 1.9 to - 3.2	Cationic	Cationic
(6) 5 ml 2M HCOONa + 5 ml 2M HCOOH + 90 ml 1M NaNO ₃ *(0.1M)	- 0.1 to - 1 (having a tendency to precipitate)	- 2.4 to - 3.8	Cationic	Cationic

pH = constant, ionic strength = 1, formate variable.
* Concentration of formate ion in solution.

TABLE 3

Carrier electrolyte	Distance migrated in cm ('+' anionic movement ; '-' cationic movement)			
	Fe(III)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)
(1) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 1 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + 24 ml water (pH = 5.15)	+1.8 to +3.9	+2.4 to +5.6	Cationic	Cationic
(2) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 2.5 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + 22.5 ml water (pH = 4.75)	+0.8 to +1.9	+2.6 to +4.6	Cationic	Cationic
(3) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 5 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + 20 ml water (pH = 4.45)	+0.5 to +2.1	+2.1 to +3.7	Cationic	Cationic
(4) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 10 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + 15 ml water (pH = 4.15)	+0.5 to +1.6	-0.6 to -1.9	Cationic	Cationic
(5) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 15 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + 10 ml water (pH = 3.97)	+0.2 to +1.1	-0.9 to -2.6	Cationic	Cationic
(6) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 20 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + 5 ml water (pH = 3.85)	+0.1 to +1.1 and -0.8 to -1.6	-1.1 to -2.6	Cationic	Cationic
(7) 25 ml 2M HCOONa + 25 ml 2M HCOOH + 50 ml 1M NaNO ₃ + (pH = 3.75)	+0.1 to 1 and -1.9 to -2.7	-1 to -3.1	Cationic	Cationic

(Formate concentration and ionic strength constant, pH is variable)

All electrolytes in Table 2 have the same pH and it will be equal to the pK_a of formic acid because of the same concentration of salt and acid. Hence, pH is 3.75 in all the cases and

$$[H_3^+] = 18 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g-ion/litre}$$

Concentration of H^+ is essential to calculate the ionic strength of the electrolyte because formic acid is a weak acid as it does not undergo complete dissociation.

Table 2 shows that Fe(III) ion behaves as an anionic complex throughout the concentration range (1M to 0.2M) of sodium formate when the pH and the ionic strength of the carrier electrolyte are constant. But at low concentration (0.1M) of Na-formate, Fe(III) moves towards the cathode. Cu(II) forms anionic complex when concentration of sodium formate is high (1M to 0.5M) but below this concentration Cu(II) forms cationic species with carrier electrolyte under the same condition. In the case of Ni(II) and Co(II), both the ions move as cationic species throughout the experiment. Hence it can be concluded that the relative stability of Fe(III)-formate complex is more than that of Cu(II)-formate complex.

Table 3 indicates that Fe(III) forms anionic complex with the carrier electrolyte throughout the experiment (pH 5.15-3.75) but at pH 3.85 and 3.75, Fe(III) forms both anionic and cationic

species when ionic strength of the electrolyte and Na-formate concentration are constant. Cu(II) forms anionic formate complex at pH 5.15-4.45 and forms cationic species at pH 4.15-3.75. In the case of Ni(II) and Co(II) both the ions move towards the cathode throughout the experiment.

From the experimental data it can be said that the Fe(III)-formate complex is very stable but Cu(II) formate complex is not so stable. So the relative stability of Fe(III)-formate complex is higher than that of Cu(II)-formate complex.

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